

Transurethral Drainage of Prostatic Abscess/Case studyFiras Al Khatib¹, Ashraf ALakkad^{2*}, Feras Al Zoabi², Ahmed S.Tawfeeq³¹Department of Urology, Madinat Zayed Hospital, AL Dhafra Region, UAE²Department of Internal Medicine, Madinat Zayed Hospital, AL Dhafra Region, UAE³Department of Radiology, Madinat Zayed hospital, AL Dhafra Region, UAE***Corresponding Author:** Dr.Ashraf ALakkad, Department of Internal Medicine, Madinat Zayed Hospital, AL Dhafra Region, UAE.**Citation:** Ashraf ALakkad^{2*}.Transurethral Drainage of Prostatic Abscess/Case study. J ourl Clin Med and Cas Rep. 2022; 1(4): 1017.**Received:** September 24, 2022**Published:** October 17, 2022**ABSTRACT****Background:** The incidence of prostatic abscesses is approximately 0.5% in comparison to all prostate disorders, and this condition typically affects those with immunosuppression or diabetes.**Case Report:** Here, we present the case of a 51-year-old, non-diabetic, nonalcoholic male patient who developed a large prostate abscess. Initially, the patient presented to the emergency department with major complaints of constant urine, fever, and right loin pain over the past three days. Urine culture and abscess culture testing revealed no presence of microbes. Ultrasound findings revealed a very large prostate of 55mL with a poorly defined left paramedian collection, like an inhomogeneous hypoechoic area. The ultrasound examination findings of the kidney, ureter, and bladder were all found to be normal. Later, a urethrocytoscopy revealed a normal urethra but an enlarged prostate with several abscesses in both the left and right lobes. During this procedure, a resection, abscess drainage, and cavity cleaning were performed. The majority of the left lobe and parts of the right lobe were excised. Additionally, there was evidence of severe active granulomatous prostatitis with foci of suppurative necrosis, although no malignancy was detected. For this purpose, the patient underwent TURP (transurethral resection of the prostate) surgery. After surgery, an ultrasound examination was performed. The findings revealed normal results, and the prostate's volume was decreased to 8.8 mL. This case was a unique presentation as no evidence of microbe was found in it.**Conclusion:** This case report suggests that transurethral drainage is the most effective treatment approach to prostate abscesses. This method should be taken into account for large and multiloculated abscesses.**Keywords:** Prostatic abscess, TURP, Transurethral drainage.**Introduction**

A prostate abscess is a relatively rare clinical condition that is frequently difficult to identify due to non-specific clinical signs. It may be linked to a high fatality rate, between 3 and 30 percent, which may indicate its rarity, diagnostic challenges, and inadequate therapy. It is believed to be a consequence of acute prostatitis and is marked by a purulent accumulation in one or more prostate lobes (1). Additionally, PAs are more prevalent among males in their fifties and sixties (2). Fortunately, with the initial use of antibiotics and the early identification and management of urethral gonococcal infections, the death rate has decreased from fifty percent to three percent to sixteen percent (3).

While prior to the introduction of modern antibiotic therapy, 75% of prostatic abscesses were caused by gonococcus, and the death rate ranged from 6% to 14%, evidence also indicates that only 0.2% of patients with urologic clinical presentation, and 0.5%–2.5% of individuals hospitalized for prostatic symptoms are diagnosed with prostatic abscesses (4). Furthermore, the predisposing factors for the development of a prostate abscess include bladder outlet obstruction, cirrhosis, indwelling catheter, chronic renal failure, hemodialysis, instrumentation of the lower urinary tract, acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS), acute and chronic bacterial prostatitis, and diabetes mellitus (3).

Studies have also shown that prostate abscesses are typically linked to slow-evolving prostatitis that has been previously detected and frequently occur in diabetic or immunosuppressed patients (5). It is detected in 1 to 2% of individuals with prostate symptoms, and because it can be challenging to diagnose clinically, clinicians occasionally rely on transrectal ultrasound (TRUS) to confirm their findings. This case report discusses the case of a 51-year-old male whose prostate abscess was successfully treated with transcutaneous drainage.

Case Report

The 51-year-old, non-diabetic, nonalcoholic male patient presented to the emergency department with major complaints of constant urine, fever, and right loin pain over the past three days. The patient had no significant past medical history, and he particularly did not have a personal or family history of any chronic disorder. There were no other complaints. He was fine before the development of urinary obstruction.

He was immediately admitted to the emergency department, and a urinary catheterization was performed, via which 1000 mL of urine was drained. A urine sample was taken from this. To rule out this pathology, a urine culture, which indicated no growth of microbes, was performed. Doctors suspected that the abscess could have been what caused this blockage. Therefore, an abscess culture was performed. It indicated no growth of microbes. Afterward, an ultrasound of the kidneys, ureters, and bladder was performed. The findings revealed a normally shaped and sized right kidney with a normal echogenic

pattern and corticomedullary differentiation. Parenchymal thickness was found to be normal. Additionally, no detectable stone masses or cysts were found during an ultrasound examination.

Similarly, the examination of the left kidney revealed a normally sized and shaped left kidney with a normal echogenic pattern and corticomedullary differentiation. Additionally, the parenchymal thickness was found to be normal, and no identifiable stones masses or cysts were spotted in the ultrasound examination. Moreover, the clamped catheter was seen to be passed through the urinary bladder. There seemed to be no gross masses. Bladder wall thickness was normal, and there were no identifiable stones. However, the prostate was found to be enlarged with a poorly defined left paramedian collection like an inhomogeneous hypoechoic area seen 2.2x1.8cm, and the prostatic volume was 55mL.

Later, the patient underwent a computerized tomography scan with and without IV contrast. The findings revealed a multilocular collection in the prostate gland, along with peripheral enhancement, an abscess of the largest size of 38x26mm on the left side, a catheter in the urinary bladder, and a normal liver size with regular boundaries and no evidence for the focal lesion. Additionally, there was no evidence of dilated intrahepatic biliary passages. Moreover, the CBD caliber, spleen, pancreas, and both kidneys were found to be normal. There was no marked evidence of focal lesion, dilatation, or stone in either of these structures. Also, no free air was found floating around these structures.

At this time, the only diagnosis was a prostate abscess. To further evaluate the diagnosis, the patient was asked to undergo Human Immunodeficiency Virus testing, which turned out to be negative. Later, the patient underwent a urethrocytoscopy that showed a normal urethra but an enlarged prostate with multiple abscesses in both the left and right lobes. During this procedure, a resection was performed, the abscesses were drained, and the cavities were cleaned. Most of the left lobe was resected, and a partial resection of the right lobe was performed. Additionally, the middle lobe was resected, and the hemostasis was secured. A foley catheter was passed of gauge number fr 22 with three openings.

Microbiology testing showed multiple fragments of prostatic tissue showing dense acute and chronic inflammations with variably formed epithelioid granuloma. We found marked evidence of foci of necrosis, associated with a neutrophilic collection indicative of suppurative necrosis. Additionally, the focal prostatic urethral lining was noted, while no acid-fast bacilli or fungal elements were seen by well-controlled GMS and PAS-D special stains.

Based on all these examinations and laboratory testing, the patient was found to have a prostate abscess, which was removed via transurethral resection. Additionally, we noted evidence of severe active granulomatous prostatitis with foci of suppurative necrosis, although no malignancy was detected. These findings suggested that the patient should undergo surgery.

A post-surgery ultrasound of the prostate, kidneys, bladder, and ureter was performed. The findings revealed a normally shaped and sized right kidney with a normal echogenic pattern and good corticomedullary differentiation. The parenchymal thickness was also found to be normal. Additionally, no detectable stone masses or cysts were found during the ultrasound examination. Similarly, the left kidney examination revealed a normally sized and shaped left kidney with a normal echogenic pattern and good corticomedullary differentiation. Additionally, the parenchymal thickness was found to be normal, and no identifiable stones masses or cysts were seen in the ultrasound examination.

Furthermore, the bladder showed normal filling of urine, no gross masses, normal wall thickness, and no stones. Moreover, the pre-void volume was found to be 338 mL, and the post-void volume, 29

mL. Meanwhile, the prostate volume was 8.8 mL, which decreased by quite a lot after the surgery. Additionally, the patient received Meropenem upon his admission to the hospital and was prescribed Levofloxacin following his discharge.

Figures: A, B and C : CT abdomen.

Discussion

A prostatic abscess is a rare clinical condition that presents with non-specific symptoms, making it difficult to identify. The symptoms and clinical manifestations of prostatic abscesses are highly variable. The most common symptoms of acute prostatitis include fever and frequent, painful urination (6, 7). Although our patient was also found to have symptoms of fever, he was not urinating at all due to a large prostatic abscess. Additionally, studies report that a prostatic abscess can spontaneously fistulize into the rectum, urinary bladder, perineum, or prostatic urethra. In some cases, it may result in sepsis and death (8). Therefore, both an accurate diagnosis and an effective treatment are necessary. The majority of published data on prostatic abscesses are case reports, and diagnostic and treatment procedures are not standardized (1).

Additionally, the risk factors associated with the development of prostate abscess include urethral stricture, history of prostate biopsy, and complicated diabetes mellitus (9). According to other studies, men with PA are up to 66% more likely to have diabetes mellitus, and 8–11% more likely to have had a previous prostate biopsy (10). Moreover, immunosuppression brought on by hemodialysis for liver cirrhosis, renal failure, and immunosuppressive drugs like chemotherapy have all been linked to the development of PA (11). In addition, the most common risk factors include recent lower urinary tract instrumentation indwelling catheters and the obstruction of the bladder outflow (12). Our case was a unique presentation as no such risk factor was found in our case.

Furthermore, as far as an accurate diagnostic test for the accurate diagnosis of the prostate abscess is concerned, the transrectal ultrasound of the prostate is the preferred diagnostic technique, as it supports the treatment and follow-up of patients with prostatic abscesses (13). According to previous studies, the most frequent observations regarding prostatic abscesses on ultrasound imaging include the presence of one or more hypoechoic zones, primarily located in the transition and central zones of the prostate, that are infiltrated by hyperechogenic areas and have a distorted glandular structure (9). This discovery supports the use of transrectal ultrasonography for the diagnosis of prostatic abscesses to detect any gas in the fluid or extra-prostatic collections.

Additionally, the most effective treatment option for prostatic abscesses is transurethral drainage. According to a previous study conducted by El-Shazly et al., men with PA who had transurethral drainage had a 100% success rate (4). Along with transurethral unroofing, the transurethral resection of the prostate (TURP) is another known procedure that has been found to be very effective (14). (TU). Although Elisha et al. reported an 83% success rate via transurethral resection on 30 patients, they also noted some side effects that required additional care, including urethral diverticulum, septic shock, urethral stricture, and epididymo-orchitis(15). However, in our case, the transurethral resection of the prostate was found to be the most effective technique with a 100 % success rate, and no side effect was reported as a result of this procedure.

Conclusion

A prostatic abscess is a very uncommon clinical illness that is often difficult to diagnose due to non-specific clinical symptoms. Patients with this condition most commonly complain of frequent painful urination and fever. If not treated early, it can result in sepsis and

the patient's death. Consequently, both an accurate diagnosis and a successful course of treatment are required. Additionally, according to previous studies, the most common treatment option is the transurethral resection of the prostate, which was also found to be a very effective treatment approach in this case as our patient was successfully treated with this technique without any side effects. However, most information about prostatic abscesses has been published in case reports, and the diagnosis and treatment processes are not standardized.

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